

The hydroxycitronellal therefore must be acting as bidentate ligand.

The metal ligand stability constants were calculated by Job's method⁵ of formula

$$K = \frac{X}{(a_1 - X)(b_1 - X)} = \frac{X}{(a_2 - X)(b_2 - X)}$$

where a_1, a_2 are the concentrations of metal and b_1, b_2 are the concentrations of ligand at different dilutions.

Values of stability constants were further confirmed by Bjerrum method⁶ as modified by Irving and Rossotti

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(v'' - v') N + E^\circ + TL^\circ (Y - \bar{n}A)}{(v'' + v') \bar{n}ATM^\circ}$$

All the above studies confirmed the complexation ratio to be 1 : 2.

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Determination of Stability Constants of 5-Methyl-Salicylidene-*p*-Methylaniline Complexes with Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+}

M. S. MAYADEO and V. P. DHAKAPPA

Department of Chemistry, Ramnarain Ruia College, Bombay-400 019

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IN the present communication the successive stability constants of the complexes of 5-methyl-salicylidene-*p*-methylaniline with various trivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum *pH* titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 5-methyl-salicylidene-*p*-methylaniline was prepared by the method described in literature², and was repeatedly crystallised. (Observed m.p. 106°, Reported m.p. 106°).

Dioxan used was purified by usual method reported in literature³. The medium of titration was 75 : 25 percent (v/v) dioxan-water mixture. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength. The titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere.

The metal perchlorates were prepared from the metal carbonates of A.R. grade supplied by S.D. Lab. Chem., Bombay, using perchloric acid of A.R. grade. All these were standardised complexometrically⁴ by E.D.T.A. titrations. All the measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The Corning Model 12 with a combined glass electrode and a calomel electrode was used.

The experimental details and computational methods are the same as described in the earlier communication⁵. The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and *pL*. The appropriate corrections for the H^+ ion concentrations have been made as per the work of Irving and Mahnot⁶ and the values have been accordingly modified. Appropriate ion corrections were made at high *pH*. The titrations were performed in duplicate to test the reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

It may be stated here that the reagent does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the titration and by the absence of any significant drift in *pH* meter readings even after one hour.

In the ligand it is the phenolic (OH) group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y', the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

The curve between 'B' and the corresponding \bar{n}_A value was plotted to get the formation curve. The formation curve extends over a range of $0.35 < \bar{n}_A < 1.95$ and is wave-like. The value of pK_1^H , which corresponds to the association of phenolic (OH) group, was evaluated from the half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$, while that of pK_2^H , which corresponds to the association of proton to imino-nitrogen was

obtained at $\bar{n}_A=1.5$. These values were further corroborated from the plots of

$$\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A} \right] \text{ vs } B \text{ and } \log \left[\frac{2-\bar{n}_A}{\bar{n}_A-1} \right] \text{ vs } B \text{ respectively.}$$

\bar{n} and pL values were calculated and \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complex-ion equilibria. From the formation curves, the values of stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were evaluated which correspond to 1:1 complex at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and 1:2 complex at $\bar{n}=1.5$ respectively. These were further corroborated by plotting $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}} \right]$ vs pL and $\log \left[\frac{2-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}-1} \right]$ vs pL graphs, respectively.

The formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complex is represented below:

In all the cases, stabilities of 1:1 complexes were evaluated, while in the cases of Y^{3+} , Nd^{3+} and Gd^{3+} stabilities of 1:2 complexes were also evaluated. The $\log K_2$ for others could not be evaluated due to precipitation probably due to metal ion hydrolysis. The order of stability of trivalent metal-chelates was found to be

TABLE I—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

Cations	$t=25^\circ C$					
	H^+	Y^{3+}	Pr^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Gd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}
$\log K_1$	11.38	7.82	7.73	6.88	7.66	7.45
$\log K_2$	3.80	7.02	—	6.18	6.83	—

* For proton association (H^+), K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species LH and LH_2^+ respectively, while for metal ions K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species ML_1 and ML_2 respectively.

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Quinoxaline Complexes with Some Mercury(II) Salts

RAGHUVIR SINGH*

Department of Chemistry, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong -793 003, Meghalaya

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THE complexes of quinoxaline (Q) with several transition metal salts have been studied by various workers¹⁻⁵ and here are described those formed by interaction with Hg(II) chloride, bromide, cyanide and thiocyanate. These complexes have been characterized by molar conductance, molecular weight, IR and far-IR spectral measurements down to 200 cm^{-1} .

The chloro-, bromo- and cyano-complexes were prepared by adding an excess of the ligand solution in ethanol to a hot solution of the metal salt in the same solvent. The thiocyanato complex was prepared by boiling a suspension of the metal thiocyanate with an excess of the ligand in ethanol and filtering the solution hot. The complexes which precipitated or crystallized out were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuo. $Hg(Q)Cl_2$: m.p. 256 [Found: Hg, 50.40; Cl, 17.29, Calc.: Hg, 49.87; Cl, 17.70%]; $Hg_2(Q)Br_4$: m.p. 243 [Found: Hg, 46.88; Br, 36.67, Calc.: Hg, 47.07; Br, 37.64%]; $Hg(Q)(CN)_2$: m.p. >290 [Found: Hg, 52.50; Calc.: Hg, 52.35%]; $Hg(Q)(SCN)_2$: m.p. 176 d. [Found: Hg, 44.12; SCN, 26.32, Calc.: Hg, 44.84; SCN, 26.00%].

Molar conductance of $10^{-3}M$ solutions in DMF (Philips Conductivity Bridge) indicate them to be non-electrolytes, except the thiocyanato-complex which acts as a weak electrolyte. The IR spectra of

* Present address: School of Chemistry, University of Hyderabad, Hyderabad-500 001.